

THE IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES AND ADVANCED METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN THE FORMATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS AS BILINGUISTS

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Abstract. *In this article, effective pedagogical methods for bilingual education of elementary school students, methodological recommendations for the development of bilingualism, and innovative technologies that serve to increase the intellectual potential of students are discussed.*

Keywords: *thematic field, noun, pedagogical environment, bilingualism, method, cognitive ability, educational technology.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, globalization is a process that includes all spheres of human activity. If the language, which is a means of communication, was not so important in this process, the effectiveness of this process would not be so high. In our rapidly developing world, we live in a time when borders, including linguistic borders, are expanding and sometimes disappearing. More than half of the world's population speaks two or more languages on a daily basis. By the way, we are talking about a foreign language, because it is well known that most of the information on the Internet, as well as all international legal, regulatory, technical and other types of documents, are presented in a foreign language. A foreign language gives us the key to many opportunities. Foreign languages (English, Russian, French, German...) are taught as a second language in educational institutions. Bilingualism is a Latin word, "bi" means two, and "lingua" means language, that is, bilingualism. Bilinguals are people who know and can speak a second language as well as their mother tongue. People who have been able to communicate in two languages since childhood are also called bilinguals. In fact, the term refers more to bilingualism, which is formed as a result of living in a bilingual environment. The Russian language is widely used as a second language in our country. This is due to several historical changes, that is, the fact that the Russian language was the state language before the years of independence, and the process of globalization. Today, the mother tongue is considered the state language, and Russian is taught in Uzbek schools. It is taught as a second language (foreign language). Learning the Russian language is considered a complex process, and young people are lagging behind in learning a second language because Uzbek families do not have a sufficient social environment for learning the language. Solving this problem it is necessary to rely on many new pedagogical methods that can be used for students. In his research work, he has based many methods of language learning from a practical point of view.

As there are two sides of a coin, bilingualism can lead to both positive and negative aspects of a child's development. Bilingualism can improve cognitive skills such as multitasking, problem solving, and critical thinking. It also opens up new cultural and social experiences and can enhance career opportunities in a globalized world. However, bilingualism can lead to language confusion,

delayed language development, learning difficulties, reduced cognitive development, and social and emotional difficulties.

There are different forms of bilingual education, including separate instruction in two or more languages or a combination of them, and all of these are specific stages of bilingual education. According to Baker, bilingual education is two languages in more than one language. According to modern estimates, approximately 60-70 percent of the world's population speaks two languages, and bilingual education is a common approach to education around the world. It is necessary to develop and put into practice several components of bilingual education. In this regard, in order to successfully improve the language learning skills of elementary school students, it is necessary to use game types of work in the lesson, because young children for students, the game is the main form of learning about the world around them. The ability to acquire two languages at the same time lasts until about 7-8 years of age, and then, after mastering the written basics of speech, the ability to acquire the language in natural communication is common for the first time. Language acquisition, declines. People who are bilingual from birth say that they are the first to acquire two languages. In addition to the game-based methods, we will try to use the Russian language as an example of working on the basis of the concept of "Thematic Area".

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Thematic area is a whole that summarizes words that are close to each other in meaning, form, function, and type and belong to the same group. They are similar to Atov words. this word creates a field around itself.

Atov(named) word+field

Adverb: Spring

Field: the bride of the seasons, March, April, May, flower, warm weather, spring.

I think that using this pedagogical technology, that is, learning words by dividing them into groups, will greatly contribute to the increase of vocabulary. Because it is easier to remember words with similar meanings.

For example: Fish, wild animals, clothes, dishes.

Themed poles

Birds.

Sparrow(s), crow(s), rook(s), rook(s), rook(s), starling(s), ga'lka(s), magpie(s), la'stochka(s), woodpecker(s), crane(s), tit(s), bluebird, nightingale, swan(s), wildbirds, quail(s), capercaillie(s), black grouse(s), heron, eagle;

Pets:

Cow, bull, calf, calves, sheep, ram, lambs, goat, dog, puppy, puppies, cat, kitten, kitten;
herd of cows, flock of sheep, herd of horses, pasture, shepherd, shepherd;
milk, butter, sour cream, cottage cheese, cheese, meat, wool, fluff;
beef, lamb, horse meat, pork;

Wild animals:

Bear, little bear, cubs, wolf, she-wolf, cub, wolf cubs,
Fox, hare, bunnies, squirrel, baby squirrel, hedgehog, elk, moose.

Fish.

Pike, carp, crucian carp, opkun, sand, catfish, shark, bream, ukha, fish turnip, pond, scales',
worm;

Winter.

December January February, snow, snowflakes, cold, frost, air, temperature, day, night,

Spring.

March, April, May, sun, day, night, streams, grass, nature;

People Earth.

Rodina, region, fatherland, Uzbekistan, Ural, Ufa', Agidel, Moscow',

Kremlin, flag, coat of arms, anthem, city, village, village, capital, globe,

I am human.

I, arm(s), palm(s), leg(s), head, nose, eye(s), look, face, forehead, lips, mouth, teeth, neck,
ear(s), eyebrow(s), veiko(s), hair,

My friend is the computer.

Computer, monitor, keyboard, mouse, processor, printer, scanner, photocopier, laptop, file,
website,

Internet, space bar, personal disk, floppy disk, flash drive, computer science, projector,
small, powerful, pocket, digital, liquid crystal, plasma, new, old, print, play, enter, freeze, read
information, copy, save, delete, exit, load, reload, turn on, view, turn off.

The following thematic area and the words around it have a common meaning, so they remain well in the student's memory and facilitate the process of language acquisition. The student's vocabulary increases. He can express his thoughts in a wide and comprehensive way even when he is searching. Oral speech is well formed. It is possible to organize didactic games using the thematic area.

For example:

The teacher says a word that reflects the thematic field. The student fills in this field.

Teacher: My friend is computer

Pupil: site, keyboard, monitor, screen, mouse

In this way, it will be more appropriate if it is expressed verbally or using drawings.

Мой друг компьютер.

Figure-1. Мой друг компьютер. (my friend computer)

Figure-2: my birthday.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Learning a second language is difficult for a child who grows up speaking one language from a young age. We can learn about this from the research of psychologist Ellen Bialystok. According to the results of the research, the vocabulary of children who speak one language is better than those who speak two languages, and also monolingual children also performed better on language tasks. But when the study was repeated a few years later among adults, bilinguals fared better than monolinguals. The fact is that although children lag behind their monolingual peers in the process of acquiring two languages, over the years this delay can be replaced by an advance.

I believe that the method of the thematic area reflected above will be effective as a pedagogical tool that contributes to the development of a Blingvist. In fact, being bilingual always

brings a number of conveniences. you can do it not only at school, but at home, paying more attention to your child. As an uncomfortable and interesting situation that occurs not only in bilingual people, but in general, in all foreign language learners, a word "turns around" at the tip of the tongue at the right time. If we fully understand the capabilities of a bilingual person, the desire to educate our children as bilingual in the future will certainly be born today. What needs to be done to implement this process.

Growing up in a bilingual family. This is the most effective way to deal with your children.

Moving to study, work, live in foreign countries with a language different from your mother tongue. In this situation, not only you, but also your children can develop bilingualism.

The existence of a personal desire to learn a second language. Language learning is not just a fun process, it is a cognitive process that requires special attention and effort. For those who are interested in intellectual work, language learning can be a truly enjoyable endeavor.

Because of the religious motive. For many centuries, the process of learning a second language to receive religious education has been taking place. In this case, learning a second language can be done first in the family, and then according to a person's own desire.

Studies show that bilingualism can indeed offer cognitive advantages. Canadian scientist and psychologist Ellen Bialystok's research on "Bilingualism: Implications for Mind and Brain" shows that bilingual children often have better executive functions. These functions include attentional control, problem-solving skills, and task-switching skills. Imagine your child having the ability to focus and manage tasks - sounds like a pretty smart advantage, doesn't it?

Let's put the hype aside and nurture our children's interest in the second language. Although it may seem like they are taking a little longer to develop their language skills, they are building a strong foundation in both languages. They are like linguistic athletes. and their brains are getting a lot of exercise. Don't be upset if your bilingual child's first words seem to be coming a little later. Research shows that bilingual children may actually start speaking a little later than their monolingual peers. However, this delay is temporary and often evens out as they grow. They are learning two languages at the same time, which may require a little more time for their linguistic mechanisms to synchronize.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, raising bilingual children has many cognitive benefits. Not only are they learning two languages, but they are developing advanced executive functions, problem-solving skills, and flexibility. Although they may begin to speak a little later, their linguistic journey equips them with lifelong cognitive skills. The positive effects of bilingualism are not limited to childhood; it can affect academic performance and even contribute to your strengths in subjects like math. So if you're thinking about taking your child on a bilingual trip, remember that you're not just teaching them languages, you're giving them the gift of cognitive excellence that will serve them well throughout their lives. It's time to embrace the wonderful world of bilingualism and watch your child's cognitive abilities flourish," said researcher Ellen Bialystok. Undoubtedly, a child who is brought up by adults who speak only one language will develop into bilingual by himself.

All of the processes listed above do not correspond to our social living environment. It is definitely limited materially and spiritually for some people.

Our hope as educators is as follows:

- improving the education system,
- creating new pedagogical methods,

- enriching the school library with literature related to language learning,
 - being able to make students interested in the lesson
 - always work on yourself
 - to create an environment for learning a second language as a mother tongue at school
- Parents are required not to be indifferent to their child's future.

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